

Potential of Aqueous Extract of *Jatropha Curcas* on the Control of Post-Harvest Rot of Sweet Orange (*Citrus Sinensis* L.) Fruits in Wukari

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Abstract

The study was conducted in Wukari Local Government Area of Taraba State, located in North-Eastern region of Nigeria on Longitude 9.783°E and Latitude 7.850°N. A total of ninety (90) sweet orange fruits (*Citrus sinensis*) were collected from three different markets within Wukari town between the months of March 2018 and June 2018. Observation for the level of fungal growth and fruit rot was made daily for 7 days and results were recorded, percentage rot severity was determined. Wukari New Market had the highest percentage incidence in the study area (83 %), followed by Wukari Yam Market (66.7 %). The least rot incidence was recorded in Wukari Old Market (60 %). Among the three isolates, *A. niger* causes the most severe rot. Mycelia covering up to 85.8%, the pathogenic effect was rated highly pathogenic. While *Aspergillus* sp. causes least severe rot with mycelia covering up to 39.9%, the pathogenic effect was rated moderately resistance. Leaves and seeds of the test plant were thoroughly washed, air dried and grinded separately into a fine powder using mortar and pestle. For seeds extraction, four different dilution concentrations were prepared by adding 5g, 10g, 15g, and 20g of the fine powder into a 100mls distilled water separately in a 250ml beaker. It was left to stand for 24 hours and then filtered through three fold of sterile cheesecloth to obtain crude aqueous extracts. For leaves extraction, only the highest dilution concentration of the seed extraction was used. The phytochemical characteristics of the plants investigated are summarized as Alkaloid, Glycosides, Terpenoids, and Saponins were present in seed and leaf extracts. Flavonoids were absent in both seed and leaf extracts. Tannins, Reducing sugar and Phenols are only present in the leaf extract. The design was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replicates. The variables considered were fungal isolates and concentrations of the extracts. All data were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program. Means that are significant were separated by the test of Least Significance Difference (LSD). The study recommends that this promising plant extract be further evaluated in multi-location that share same agroecology zone

Keywords: Aqueous, Extracts, *Jatropha*, Post-harvest, Rot and Lemon

INTRODUCTION

Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L.) which belong to the family Rutaceae, It is mainly cultivated in the tropical and subtropical regions of the world in over 137 countries on six continents (Ismail and Zhang, 2004). Sweet orange is an important fruit crop in international trade next to grapes (*Citrus* Commodity Notes, 2005). World orange production was estimated to be 69.41 million metric tons annually (2012). It is one of the major commercial fruit crops that are widely consumed both as fresh fruit or juice due to its high vitamin C content and antioxidant potential (Gorinstein *et al.*, 2001).

In spite of all these benefits, the plant is besieged by lots of fungal pathogens that cause postharvest diseases, such as rot of fruits, which causes significant economic losses (Poppe *et al.*, 2001). The predominant pathogens causing the most important postharvest disease of fruits worldwide belong to the genus *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* (Poppe *et al.*, 2001). Poor handling, packaging, storage, and transportation of oranges result in the decay and growth of microorganisms (Wilson *et al.* 1991). Orange fruits, due to their low pH, higher moisture content and nutrient composition made them very susceptible to attack by pathogenic fungi, which also make them unfit for consumption due to the production of mycotoxins (Moss, 2002).

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Synthetic fungicides are the common control measure practice by farmers for being effective and fast (Guptan and Dikshit, 2010). However, these synthetic pesticides and their residues are not biodegradable and pose a lot of problems, causing damage to the environment and humans (Nichoison, 2007). Searching for new types of pesticides which are effective, biodegradable and suitable for used is necessary. In view of that, this study aimed at testing the potential of aqueous extracts of *Jatropha curcas* in the management of fungi associated with the postharvest rot of sweet orange fruits in Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Wukari Local Government Area of Taraba State, located in North-Eastern region of Nigeria on Longitude 9.783°E and Latitude 7.850°N. The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Biological Sciences Department, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Samples Collection

A total of ninety (90) sweet orange fruits (*Citrus sinensis*) were collected from three different markets within Wukari town between the months of March 2018 and June 2018. The markets are Wukari new market, Wukari old market, and Wukari yam market. Thirty healthy orange fruits were later obtained in the same markets for the pathogenicity test. All the samples collected were placed in sterile polythene bags separately labelled and transported to the Laboratory for further studies. The plant materials used in the control of fungi in this study was obtained in Wukari town and was identified as *Jatropha curcas* in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria with an identification number (V/No. 22873).

Estimation of Disease Incidence

The orange samples were sorted based on the extent of rotten, and the percentage rot incidence was estimated using the formula below;

$$\text{Percentage rots incidence} = \frac{\text{Number of Infected Fruits}}{\text{Total Number of Fruits Collected}} \times 100$$

Isolation and Identification of Fungi

The procedures described by Burgess *et al.* (2008) were used for the isolation of fungi from rotten oranges in this study. The infected orange samples were washed in tap running water to remove dirt; the samples were then surface sterilized with cotton wool soaked in absolute ethanol. The fruits were then cut into small segments (about 3mm diameter) using sterilized scalpel dipped in absolute ethanol before rinsing in three changes of sterile distilled water. The segments were then aseptically placed near the edges of the Petri dishes (90mm diameter) containing freshly prepared solidified Potato Dextrose agar (PDA) and incubated at room temperature and were observed daily. The fungi isolated thereof were identified using cultural and morphological features as well as microscopic examination using slide culture techniques as described by Oyeleke and Manga (2008). The isolates were compared with fungi structures in the Atlases by Snowdon (1990) and Watanabe (2005).

Pathogenicity Test

The procedures described by Burgess *et al.* (2008) were used for ascertaining the pathogenicity of the fungi isolated in this study. Healthy fruits were surface sterilized with absolute ethanol. Cylindrical plug tissues were cut out from the fruits using a sterilized 5mm sized cork borer. Agar disc containing one week old fungal culture were aseptically placed in these holes, were then covered and sealed with petroleum jelly. The procedure was replicated three times for each fungal isolates. The inoculated oranges and the control oranges were placed in a separate sterile incubator at room temperature for 7 days. The point of inoculation of each type of fungus was examined and recorded. The diameter of the rotten portion of the orange fruits was measured. The fungi were later re-isolated from the inoculated fruits and compared with the initial isolates.

Determination of Rot Severity

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Observation for the level of fungal growth and fruit rot was made daily for 7 days and results were recorded, percentage rot severity was determined to adopt the method of (Balogun *et al.*, 2005; and Zakari *et al.*, 2015). By this method, a fungus was considered pathogenic on the fruit if new mycelia emerged and extended radially and upwards from the originally inoculated disc and became visible outside the original wound hole on the fruit surface thereby causing fruit rot. Percentage rot severity was determined using the formula below;

$$\text{Percentage rot severity} = \frac{\text{Diameter of rot covered}}{\text{Diameter of fruit surface}} \times 100$$

The rot/ disease severity was categorized following the severity scale (Paul *et al.*, 2008) as follows shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Percentage of Rot Severity

Severity score	Fruit surface affected (%)	Category
0	0	Highly resistant
1	1-10	Resistant
2	11-20	
3	21-30	Moderately resistant
4	31-40	
5	41-50	Intermediate
6	51-60	Susceptible
7	61-70	
8	71-80	Highly susceptible
9	81-90	
10	91-100	

Preparation of Plant Extracts

The approach of Taiga (2010) and (Zakari *et al.*, 2015) was employed for the plant extraction. Leaves and seeds of the test plant were thoroughly washed, air-dried and ground separately into a fine powder using mortar and pestle. For seeds extraction, four different dilution concentrations were prepared by adding 5g, 10g, 15g, and 20g of the fine powder into a 100mls distilled water separately in a 250ml beaker. It was left to stand for 24 hours and then filtered through three fold of sterile cheesecloth to obtain crude aqueous extracts. For leaves extraction, only the highest dilution concentration of the seed extraction was used.

Testing the Effect of *Jatropha curcas* on Fungal Isolates

Poison food technique as adopted by Zakari *et al.* (2015) was used in testing the effect of the test plant on fungal isolates; 2 mls of different concentrations of *J. curcas* extracts were aseptically poisoned into 10 mls of PDA medium separately using a sterile string and needle. The mixture was rotated gently to homogenize and was allowed to solidify. Each plate was inoculated with fungal isolate by placing a 5mm diameter plug taken from the advancing edges of 7-day old culture using sterile cork borer and inoculated in the center of the medium. The same procedure was adopted for other isolates. In the control plates, sterile distilled water was used instead of the extracts. Each examination was replicated three times. Mycelial growth diameter of each isolate was measured and recorded when the growths of the isolates were completed in the control treatment. Data were transformed into inhibition or stimulation percentages by using the following formula.

$$\text{Inhibition percentage} = \text{DC-DT/DC} \times 100$$

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$$\text{Stimulation percentage} = \frac{\text{DT}-\text{DC}}{\text{DT}} \times 100$$

Where DC - Average Diameter of fungal spore in control.

DT - Average diameter of fungal spore with treatment.

Phytochemical Analysis

The individual phytochemical was extracted in the suitable solvent using soxlet extractor and the crude extracts were stored in air-tight containers at 40⁰C till further use as described by (Alade and Irobi, 1998). And some components of the phytochemical were analyzed using different qualitative tests for Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Saponin, Tannin, Terpenoids, Glycosides, Reducing sugar and phenols as according to the method of Sofawaro (1993).

Experimental Design and Statistical Analysis

The design was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replicates. The variables considered were fungal isolates and concentrations of the extracts. All data were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program. Means that are significant were separated by the test of Least Significance Difference (LSD) at p: 0.05 (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Results and Discussion

Percentage fungal rot incidence on the Sweet orange fruits are presented in Table 2, of the three markets surveyed, Wukari New Market had the highest percentage incidence in the study area (83 %), followed by Wukari Yam Market (66.7 %). The least rot incidence was recorded in Wukari Old Market (60 %).

Three fungi were isolated from the sweet orange fruits collected and were identified as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus sp.* and *Geotrichum candidum* Plates 1-3. Akintobi *et al.* (2011) reported *Aspergillus* species associated with spoilage of orange fruits in Nigeria.

Among the three isolates, *A. niger* causes the most severe rot. Mycelia covering up to 85.8%, the pathogenic effect was rated highly pathogenic. While *Aspergillus sp.* causes least severe rot with mycelia covering up to 39.9%, the pathogenic effect was rated moderately resistance Table 3. The high pathogenic level of *Aspergillus niger* could be due to the presence of toxins that might have been released into the oranges during storage. Al-Hindi *et al.* (2011) reported that toxigenic fungi produce mycotoxins which cause spoilage in fruits. Balogun *et al.* (2005) also found *Aspergillus niger* as the most virulence among fungi isolated from the pepper. *Aspergillus* spp. are known to produce several toxic metabolites, such as malformins, naphthopyrones (Frisvad and Samson, 1991; Pitt and Hocking, 1997) and they can produce Ochratoxins (OTA), a mycotoxin which is a very important toxin worldwide because of the hazard it poses to human and animal health (Peraica *et al.*, 1999; Petzinger and Weidenbach, 2002). From Table 5, *Jatropha curcas* seed extract reduced the mycelial growth of the two *Aspergillus* species up to 26.47% and 46.47% at 15% concentration, and up to 36.70 % at 20% concentration. However, there were stimulations in the mycelial growth of these fungi at lower concentrations. The extract shows inhibitory effects at all concentrations on *G. candidum* except at 20% concentration where 10.90% stimulatory effect was observed. Table 6 indicated that leaf extract of the test plant inhibited mycelial growth of *A. sp.* and *G. candidum* up to 23.60% and 16.53 respectively, but stimulated mycelial growth of *A. niger* up to only 6.09%. This implies that *J. curcas* can be effective in controlling fungal growth, still can create the ambient condition for the growth of these fungi. This agrees with the findings of Isawunmi (1984) who reported *Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp. as common rot causal agents of *J. curcas*. This explains why it stimulates the growth of the fungal isolates in our study. Donlaporn *et al* (2010) also reported antifungal effects of *J. curcas* on seven fungal species. However, none of these fungal species were isolated in this study. The difference could be due to a different method of extraction, the concentration used or fungal isolates. Comparing the effect our plant extracts with synthetic fungicide (Mancozeb) on the inhibition of the fungal isolates indicated that synthetic fungicide has a better result than aqueous seed and leaf extract. Generally, the pesticide used had significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) inhibited all the fungi isolates as compared to the effect recorded by the seed and leaf extracts of *J. curcas*.

The phytochemical characteristics of the plants investigated are summarized in Tables 6. Alkaloid, Glycosides, Terpenoids, and Saponins were present in seed and leaf extracts. Flavonoids were absent in both

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seed and leaf extracts. Tannins, Reducing sugar and Phenols are only present in the leaf extract. Njoku *et al.* (2007) reported reasonable quantities of Alkaloids, Glycosides, and Terpenoids in *J. curcas* leaves and seeds extracts. This explains their presence in our extracts. These phytochemicals might be responsible for the antifungal properties of the extract.

Table 2: Percentage Rot Incidence of Sweet Oranges in Wukari Market

Markets	No. of fruits collected	No. of rotten fruits	Rot incidence (%)
New market	30	25	83.0
Yam market	30	20	66.7
Old market	30	18	60.0
Total	90	63	70.0

Plate 1: Culture and Micrograph of *Aspergillus niger* Van Tiegh

Plate 2: Culture and Micrograph of *Aspergillus* sp. Sect Wentii)

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Plate 3: Culture and Micrograph of *Geotrichum candidum* Link)

Table 3: Fungal Rot Severity of *Citrus sinensis*

Fungal isolates	Fruit surface affected (%)	Severity	score	Category
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	85.8	9		Highly susceptible
<i>Geotrichum candidum</i>	73.0	8		Highly susceptible
<i>Aspergillus spp.</i>	39.9	4		Moderately resistance
Mean	66.3	7		
LSD	25.6	2.35		
p-Value	0.05	0.05		

Table 4: Effect of Seed Extract on Fungal Isolates

Conc. (g/v)	Reduction/Stimulation (%)		
	<i>A. Niger</i>	<i>A. spp.</i>	<i>G. candidum</i>
5%	24.13 (S)	12.27(S)	9.43(I)
10%	29.33(S)	13.60(S)	16.57(I)
15%	26.47(I)	46.47(I)	19.97(I)
20%	31.40(S)	36.70(I)	10.90(S)
Control (-ve)	100(I)	100(I)	100(I)
Control (+ve)	0.00(N)	0.00(N)	0.00(N)
Mean	27.83	27.26	14.22
LSD	6.79	40.56	20.66
P-value	0.05	0.05	0.05

Key

I= Growth reduction

S= Growth stimulation

N=No effect

Table 5: Effect of leaf extract on fungal isolates

Fungal isolates	Reduction/Stimulation (%)
<i>A. niger</i>	6.09 (S)
<i>A. spp</i>	23.60 (I)
<i>G. candidum</i>	16.53 (I)
Control (-ve)	100 (I)
Control (+ve)	0.00 (N)
Mean	15.41
LSD	13.38
P-value	0.05

Key

I= Growth reduction

S= Growth stimulation

N=No effect

Table 6: Qualitative Determination of Phytochemical Groups of Extract

Phytochemical	Result	
	Leaf	Seed
Alkaloids	+	+
Flavonoids	-	-
Saponins	+	+
Tannins	+	-
Terpenoids	+	+
Glycosides	+	+
Reducing sugars	+	-
phenols	+	-

Key

+ = Present

- = Absent

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study revealed that *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus* sp, and *Geotrichum candidum* were fungi associated with Sweet orange rots in Wukari. That the test plants; *Jatropha curcas*, have strong fungicidal properties at certain concentrations against the fungal isolates from rotted orange fruits in Wukari. That the active ingredients of the test plants can be extracted even with water and yet be effective. The presence of alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, and glycosides in both seed and leaf extracts is an indication that these four important secondary metabolites are responsible for the fungicidal activities of the extracts observed *in vitro*. These findings are very important in controlling pepper rot pathogens since unlike chemical control this would have better results as they are biologically based and environmentally safe.

Finally, it was recommended that further research should be conducted in different parts of the plant so that more potentials of the plant can be explored.

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